

Wavefunction and the Identity of a Momentum State in a Quantum Bound State Part II

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In Part I of this note, we argued that in classical statistical mechanics, the probability $P(p)$, where p is momentum, is well defined because there is a balance of two-body elastic collisions and their time-reversed reactions. In particular, this may be applied to a point x where one imagines a tiny box with many particles. In quantum bound states, collisions are with a potential and one does not have a balance of reactions and their time reversed cases. Thus, the notion of p at x does not seem to be clearly defined. A particle may be at x with momentum p , but at the same time may be reacting with $V(x)$ and transforming into another p_j . Thus, there is an ambiguity which does not exist in classical statistical mechanics. There, a particle may be colliding and so a p appears to disappear, but a new p is created by a time reversed reaction. $P(p)$, we argue, must hold over time in an equilibrium. Due to this issue, it appears that the best one may do is to define $P(p)$ for the whole x region in quantum mechanics. This $P(p)$ is measurable by taking an ensemble of identical single particles, knocking them out and measuring their momentum. As a result, knowing “ p ” exactly means one does not know “ x ”.

As a result, a different view must be taken to dealing with probabilities in a quantum bound state. We use the idea of invariance in x and argue that a wave-like behaviour in probability may be used to describe results. This is unusual because it appears as if particles are appearing or disappearing at different x points. If one has periodic motion, a question which arises is: What is the spatial frequency? We argue that the answer follows from classical physics. There: $\Delta p = \Delta t (-dV/dx)$. If $p_{\text{initial}} = 0$ and Δt is constant, one sees that a large p_{final} corresponds to a large change in $V(x)$ in a tiny dx or that there is very good resolution in x . Thus a large p (linear) implies high resolution in x . Thus, we use px as the argument of the periodic probability function.

Classical Statistical Mechanics

As argued in Part I, classical statistical mechanics (Maxwell-Boltzmann gas, but also Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein gases) may be derived by considering a balance of two body elastic collisions with their time reversed collisions i.e.

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad f(e_1)f(e_2) = f(e_3)f(e_4) \quad ((1b))$$

Taking \ln of ((1b)) and equating to ((1a)) yields the MB distribution. For the Fermi-Dirac and Bose-Einstein cases one has:

$$e_1 + e_2 = e_3 + e_4 \quad ((1a)) \quad f(e_1)[1 \mp f(e_3)] f(e_2)[1 \mp f(e_4)] = f(e_3)[1 \mp f(e_1)]f(e_4)[1 \mp f(e_2)]$$

Thus, a particle with momentum p (energy $pp/2m$) in a Maxwell-Boltzmann (MB) gas may be colliding i.e have dual identity as it is transforming, but at the same time the time-reversed reaction, which is in balance, is producing a p . Thus, it makes sense to consider $P(p)$ in this case, we argue. Furthermore, $P(p)$ makes sense at each particular x . For example in an MB

gas, one considers a small box at x which contains a large number of particles. In such a case, the balance of a time reversed reaction with the regular reaction still holds. Such does not seem to be the case in quantum mechanics.

Quantum Bound States

In a quantum bound state, the multiple identity problem of momentum state p is the same as in the classical picture i.e a particle with momentum p may interact with the potential to form a new momentum. Unlike the classical statistical case, however, there is not a time balanced reaction so there does not seem to be a clearly defined concept of $P(p)$ at x over time. As a result, one must consider an average of $P(p)$ over all x values. This leads to the quantum result $P(p)=a(p)a(p)$ where $W(x)=\text{Sum over } p a(p)\exp(ipx)$ and spatial density = $W^*(x)W(x)$. In other words, knowing the probability of p means not knowing anything about the associated x value.

Wavelike Behaviour

Given that one cannot make physical sense of $P(p)$ at x , one may still consider a mathematical $P(p/x)$. This function may have unusual statistical properties and that seems to be fine. We argue that invariance appears to be a key idea given that p should not really have uniqueness at x . One solution is $P(p/x)=\text{constant}$, but this cannot account for a changing $KE(x)=E-V(x)$. In physical problems with invariance, one often has wave solutions, such as in water waves, sound waves and waves on a string, but these are based on mechanical (Newton's law) considerations.

A different picture appears for a photon. Maxwell's electromagnetic equations suggest that a charge is the source of an electric field E and a current, of a magnetic B . If there is no charge and no current, a solution should be $E=0$ and $B=0$. Interestingly, a second solution exists, namely that of a wave for either E or B i.e. $\exp(ipx-iEt)$ because a wave equation can be created from $\text{dB}/\text{dt} = -\text{grad } x E$ and $\text{dE}/\text{dt} = \text{grad } x B$. Thus, one has the E or B equal to zero solution and a perturbed solution which oscillates about this, both in space and time. This gives rise to both positive and negative values of E and B .

In the quantum case, one might suggest a similar periodic solution about a constant probability in x . This leads to $\exp(i \text{ frequency } x)$ whose modulus is 1. The modulus of 1 ensures that probability is not lost overall, although locally a particle may lose probability or gain it or even have negative probability as one moves from one x to another. This appears counter-classical and it is because one cannot establish an identity of a particle in a particular p state because it is changing due to interactions with $V(x)$ and other p states on average combine with $V(x)$ to form p . The unusual feature is that one has a probability wave over x . At first, a random pattern might be expected, but for equilibrium an average randomness should yield a fixed pattern. We argue in the next section that the unusual feature of a probability wave in x may be linked to classical physics.

One may note that the conservation of probability leads to two dimensions i.e. a fixed radius of 1 which rotates clockwise or counterclockwise depending on the direction of motion. An important question arises as to the value of the "frequency". It should be noted that a wavelike probability will have physical consequences.

Quantum Frequency of Periodicity from Classical Physics?

We suggest that quantum spatial frequency may arise from classical physics. Consider a potential $V(x)$ which has sharp changes in value over tiny x values. In other words a sharp resolution is needed to determine such a change. At the same time, Newton's second law:

$$\Delta p = \Delta t (-dV/dx) \quad (3)$$

suggests that for fixed Δt , a large change in p (or p itself if $p_0=0$) corresponds or measures this sharp resolution. Thus, we argue that $\exp(ipx)$ is a good candidate for the probability wave. (Interestingly, it also holds for a single free quantum particle with momentum p indicating that there is already a p resolution in a classical particle leading to an unusual complex probability scheme.)

In other words, the probability wave is not so unusual if one has to establish a resolution in space which already exists in classical physics. What is unusual is that the probability for a particle with $\pm p$ changes and even becomes negative with x i.e. $\cos(px)$ for positive parity. As argued, overall probability is conserved and the identity of a particle with momentum p at x is not a given as it is in classical physics because the particle is continuously transforming from one p to another.

With probability waves one has interference i.e. positive probability values at a point x from one p may cancel/add with those of other p values.

At first, one might think that the periodicity of $\exp(ipx)$ is simply a mathematical convenience, but a superposition of $\exp(ipx)$ values leads to a periodic, real result for a bound state. Given that one cannot define $P(p)$ at x , one has interference/superposition leading to an overall $W(x)$ whose $W^*(x)W(x)$ gives the overall probability at each x point. (For a bound state, $W(x)$ turns out to be real because $\exp(ipx)$ and $\exp(-ipx)$ terms either cancel real or imaginary portions.) As a result, focusing on x leads to a loss of information about p i.e. p does appear explicitly in $W(x)$ in complete contrast to classical mechanics.

What if $P(p)$ at x Made Sense?

We have argued that $P(p)$ at x does not make sense in a quantum bound state due to a lack of balance of a reaction of p with $V(x)$ at x with the time reversed scenario. What if one has $P(p,x)$ in the classical statistical sense? One would need to have:

$$P(p,x) = 0 \text{ for large } \pm x \text{ values as in an oscillator for all } p$$

One would need $P(p,x)$ to change in a particular way in order to have $KE(x) = \sum \text{over } p \text{ } p^2/2m$
 $P(p,x) = E - V(x)$.

In such a scenario, one follows $P(p,x)$ through x for each p . This is almost the same as classical mechanics in which each p is followed through x , so this is not really a statistical approach

If one assumes that $P(p,x) = P(p)P_1(x)$ as in classical statistical mechanics, one finds that:

$$\left\{ \sum_p P(p) p^2 / 2m \right\} P_1(x) = E - V(x)$$

The term in $\{ \}$ is the same for all x points and represents energy, but what is this energy? In classical statistical mechanics it is temperature, but one does not have this concept (at least in this form) in quantum bound states.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we argue that $P(p)$, where p is momentum, is defined at x in classical statistical mechanics, but not in quantum mechanics. Thus $P(p)$ in quantum mechanics represents an average over all of x i.e. $P(p) = \int dx P(p/x)P(x)$. In other words, if one knows the probability for p exactly, one does not know anything about x .

In quantum bound states, we argue that there is no balance of collisions of p with $V(x)$ at x and the time reversed situation. Thus, $P(p)$ at x does not make sense. We argue that one may define $P(p/x)$, but that it may have unusual properties in a classical sense. Using the argument of invariance, we suggest wavelike behaviour as the underlying result, just as in invariant water, gas (sound waves) or waves on a string, but for quantum mechanics these are probability waves. It is as if a particle is more present at one x than at another and may even have negative probabilities. At first this sounds impossible, but one may have overall probability conserved at each point i.e. use $\exp(i \text{frequency } x)$ such that the modulus is 1. The identity of a particle with p at x is not a given as in classical mechanics due to continuous transformations to other p values, so the wave scenario is not so odd and may even be linked to classical physics. The question becomes what one should use as the frequency. We argue that the answer follows from classical physics i.e. Newton's second law: $\Delta p = p - p_0 = \Delta t (-dV/dx)$. For a fixed Δt , p is related to the resolution so we suggest that one may use p as the frequency i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. High p can resolve changes in very small dx . Resolution of x , however, must manifest it physically, so the idea of a changing probability $\cos(px)$ and in fact a changing physical density $W^*(x)W(x)$ to establish this resolution is needed and appears experimentally.